

On the Newman-Janis Deformation from Twistor Weyl Double Copy

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Abstract. Linearized exact vacuum metrics, such as the Kerr-Schild metrics from the twistor Weyl double copy, have no nongravitational fields or matter and additively distinguish curved spacetime from Minkowski spacetime. These properties allow linearized exact vacuum metrics to geometrically characterize the inability of a local physical theory to lift to a global physical theory in a way that does not require consideration of quantum prediction for a valid quantized gravity theory. Linearized exact vacuum metrics satisfy requirements of quantized gravity if Bell inequalities are interpreted as distinguishing quantum content (as physical locality) from quantum prediction, with quantum content of geometric/physical type (ie sheaf-cohomological/EPR type) and quantum prediction of physical type. Quantum prediction can be independent of quantized gravity as linearized gravity since quantum content is fully contained in geometric-local global obstruction as (twistor) sheaf cohomology. The Newman-Janis deformation between Schwarzschild and Kerr metrics follows as a reality condition, and minimally-coupled three-point amplitudes clarify ontological (beable) and dynamical aspects of the Newman-Janis deformation allowing for physical application of the reality condition. A discussion suggests implications for topics including quantum interpretation, cosmological inflation, and interpretation of Kerr separability of the Dirac equation.

Introduction—The double copy is a widely-studied topic in contemporary physics clarifying remarkable similarities between gauge and gravity fields [1-10]. The double copy is generally used to simplify difficult calculations or conceptual issues by translating between aspects of gauge and gravity fields using a squaring relation [7]. The broadest classification of double copies is of classical double copies [1-4, 9] and amplitude (QFT) double copies [6-8]. This paper suggests that the most relevant type of double copy for quantized gravity theory is a classical double copy, specifically the twistor Weyl double copy [1-4] between classical electromagnetic and linearized gravity fields based in (twistor) sheaf cohomology.

Sheaf-cohomological aspects of twistor theory [5] perhaps allow the geometric notion of local-global obstruction to physically characterize the local nature of quantum theory in relation to the global nature of gravitation theory. Twistor-cohomological geometric obstruction (inability to lift a local physical theory to a global theory) seems plausible as the correct mathematical framework for geometrically characterizing local physicality, especially since non-vanishing twistor cohomology is known to map to both electromagnetic and linearized gravity fields through the Penrose transform. The Penrose transform suggests that geometric local-global obstruction can field-theoretically characterize the inability of lifting a local physical theory to a global physical theory and that this lifting obstruction characterizes local physicality geometrically. A geometric characterization of local physicality as local-global obstruction allows Bell inequalities to be interpreted as distinguishing quantum content from quantum prediction implying a characterization of quantized gravity theories as physical mappings (independent of quantum prediction) from geometric local-global obstruction.

Kerr-Schild metrics [9, 10] are linearized exact vacuum gravitational field solutions that are a special case of linearized exact vacuum fields from the twistor Weyl double copy [1]. Kerr-Schild gravitational metrics can be quantum-gravitational since the twistor Weyl double copy necessitates unambiguous cohomology that fully contains quantum content within twistor-theoretic local-global obstruction mapping to linearized exact vacuum metric. The Penrose transform generates Kerr-Schild metrics from unambiguous cohomology [2, Section 3.4] necessitated by the ambiguous cohomology product of the twistor Weyl double copy in radiative [3, Section 3.5] and nonradiative [4, Section 4] aspects of gravitation. The linearized metric additively distinguishing curvature from flatness is required to characterize a physical theory from geometric local-global obstruction. The Schwarzschild and Kerr metrics have linearized and nonlinearized representations, but on this view only the linearized metrics can be considered quantum-gravitational (local-global obstruction mapped to metric additively distinguishing curvature from flatness). Vacuum solutions are required to characterize that the sheaf cohomology (geometric local-global obstruction mapping to physical fields through the Penrose transform) fully contains description of quantum content since there are no nongravitational field considerations for vacuum solutions.

The points central to the argument suggesting the Newman-Janis deformation as perhaps having aspects of quantized gravity are 1) Bell inequalities distinguish quantum content from quantum prediction to imply a characterization of quantized gravity theories as physical mappings (independent of quantum prediction) from geometric local-global obstruction 2) Kerr-Schild gravitational metrics can be quantum-gravitational since the twistor Weyl double copy necessitates unambiguous cohomology that fully contains quantum content within twistor-theoretic local-global obstruction mapping to linearized exact vacuum metric. These points suggest that the differences between Schwarzschild and Kerr metrics are especially important in understanding quantized gravity reality conditions since of the two only the Kerr metric is realistic.

Argument—Bell inequalities distinguish quantum content (as physical locality or local causality) from quantum predictions [11, 12]. Quantum content is of geometric type and physical type, with the EPR side of the Bell inequalities clarifying only the physical type of quantum content. Nonlocal interpretations [13-16] of experimental confirmation of Bell inequalities are, on this view, mistaken in not distinguishing the types (geometric/physical and physical) of the inequalities' two sides. Quantized gravity from geometric local-global obstruction as non-vanishing cohomology of sheaves characterizes the inability of a local physical theory to lift to a global physical theory. Twistor theory's Penrose transform maps from non-vanishing cohomology of sheaves (Čech [17, 18] or equivalently Dolbeault [19, 20]) to physical fields to physically characterize geometric local-global obstruction.

The twistor Weyl double copy includes the Kerr-Schild double copy between electromagnetic fields and the simplest linearized exact vacuum gravity metrics, and has "unambiguous" cohomology for radiative [3, section 3.5] and nonradiative aspects [4, Section 4]. Ambiguities arise from the cohomology product on the electromagnetic side of the classical double copy since "the notion of multiplying and dividing by cohomology classes ... is not well-defined" [3, section 3.5] and these operations on cohomology classes are required to define the twistor classical double copy.

Linearized exact vacuum metrics [21] consider no matter or nongravitational fields so the quantum content is characterized as fully within twistor sheaf cohomology as geometric local-

global obstruction. After the interpretation of Bell inequalities as distinguishing local quantum content from local quantum prediction the argument arriving at the notion of Newman-Janis reality condition does not require either local or global physical information since only local-global obstruction physical information is required to characterize quantized gravity from the Penrose transform. The linearized metric additively distinguishes local and global parts as required by the Penrose transform mapping from geometric local-global obstruction. A physical theory requiring geometric local-global obstruction mapped to a physical spacetime metric cannot map to nonlinearized spacetime metrics since nonlinearized metrics do not additively distinguish local physical theories from global physical theories; spacetime metric additivity is assumed as mathematical-physical when the field is based in an unambiguous Penrose transform and classical double copy. Linearized Kerr and Schwarzschild metrics are both suitably quantum-gravitational since they can be expressed from the Weyl double copy with unambiguous twistor cohomology; however, only the Kerr spacetime is considered as existing in the universe as emphasized by Chandrasekhar's exhilaration upon encountering the Kerr metric [22, 23]:

"In my entire scientific life, extending over forty-five years, the most shattering experience has been the realization that an exact solution of Einstein's equations of general relativity, discovered by the New Zealand mathematician, Roy Kerr, provides the absolutely exact representation of untold numbers of massive black holes that populate the universe. This shuddering before the beautiful, this incredible fact that a discovery motivated by a search after the beautiful in mathematics should find its exact replica in Nature, persuades me to say that beauty is that to which the human mind responds at its deepest and most profound."

The Newman-Janis deformation [24] relates Schwarzschild and Kerr metrics and can be considered a reality condition of (twistor) quantized gravity theories since it characterizes reality formally as a difference between the two simplest Kerr-Schild exact linearized metrics based in the twistor Weyl double copy. The Schwarzschild spacetime is too simple while the Kerr spacetime seems to make the "irreducible basic elements" required for realistic curved spacetime "as simple and as few as possible" [25].

Applications—Bell's notion of local beables [11, 26] emphasizes the importance of clarifying ontology and dynamics for physical theory and is especially helpful for difficult basic questions in quantum theory [27-31]. For applications of the twistor-cohomological argument about linearized gravity as quantized gravity it seems preliminarily useful to consider ontology as clarified by the notion of Kerr elementary particle [32] and dynamics as clarified by a worldsheet effective action [33]. These ontology and dynamics are attempted explanations of the origin of the Newman-Janis deformation and can be considered as quantum-gravitational if the deformation is based in the twistor Weyl double copy.

The Newman-Janis deformation provides an ontology based in the notion of Kerr elementary particle since "the exponentiation induced in taking the large-spin limit of minimally coupled spinning particles, precisely maps to the Newman-Janis" deformation [32]. Three-point amplitude minimal coupling is especially related to the Kerr metric [34-37] and relates the rotation Kerr parameter to the particle inertial mass and particle spin while also containing a gravitational mass term which must be equivalent to the inertial mass [32, Equation 24]. The inertial mass term is in the denominator of the equation relating the Kerr rotation to particle

spin and mass ($a = \frac{s}{m}$) implying $m > 0$. The interpretation of gravitational and inertial mass equivalence as related to three-point amplitudes follows from considering the exponentiation of the minimally coupled three-point amplitude as a 'minimal' physical basis of the Newman-Janis deformation and therefore also of the simplest Kerr-Schild metrics the deformation relates. The Kerr-Schild double copy can be connected to the non-abelian amplitude double copy using the twistor space S-matrix (based in Witten's twistor string) and a (2,2) to (3,1) analytic continuation [38-42]. The locality Wightman axiom could preserve its relevance to quantum content and quantum prediction but be extended with the condition that the local fields can be discussed also from non-vanishing cohomology as geometric local-global obstruction mapped to physical field.

Besides ontologically clarifying Kerr elementary particles in relation to the Newman-Janis deformation a dynamical account of the Newman-Janis deformation is required. The two-dimensional worldsheet effective action [33] can be considered a basic dynamical quantity related to the Newman-Janis deformation. The 2-dimensionality of this basic dynamical quantity can perhaps provide support for the 2-dimensionality of quantized gravity information theories such as quantized JT gravity [43-45] and quasi-experimental AdS_2 quantized gravity [46-48]; if the worldsheet effective action from Newman-Janis deformation is considered a basic action in quantized gravity then 2-dimensional aspects of quantized gravity appear less approximate and more directly physically-relevant.

The PBR theorem [49] distinguishes quantum information from quantum reality suggesting two types of approaches to quantized gravity theory: based in quantum information [43-48] and based in quantum reality [32, 33]. Ontology [32] and dynamics [33] from Newman-Janis deformation begins with an interpretation of Bell inequalities; therefore the PBR theorem, also a theorem about quantum content, seems to imply that quantum content contains a distinction between information and reality that is retained when quantum content is expressed cohomologically in (twistor) quantized gravity as inability to lift to a global physical theory. Bell inequalities clarify quantum content as of geometric type expressible sheaf-cohomologically and of physical type expressible by EPR-type arguments, so perhaps the binary geometric/physical type of quantum content is related to the binary information/reality distinction. On this view the PBR theorem relates solely to the quantum content side of Bell inequalities since geometric/physical type quantum content seems capable of accommodating the information-reality distinction while physical type quantum prediction seems less expressive.

Unambiguous cohomology is necessitated by the gauge side of the double copy, so this unambiguous cohomological geometry can be considered as underlying the gravitational field from the Penrose transform; therefore Kerr elementary particles seem to have a geometric aspect that can inform cosmological considerations such as inflation theory [50, 51] or primordial black holes [52], along with the physical aspect that informs physical calculations such as Kerr impulses [32, 53]. Three-point amplitude minimal coupling could underlie the quantum fluctuations relevant to the inflaton field potential. The independence of three-point amplitudes from Minkowski spacetime [42], could imply that three-point amplitude minimal coupling underlies both quantum theory and special relativity. The on-shell aspects of three-point minimal coupling can be considered to satisfy the energy-momentum relation, which could imply the energy-time uncertainty relations if the aspects of physical laws described by special relativity are assumed as underlying quantum theory. Then the framework of [54], which

combines on-shell and off-shell aspects, can perhaps clarify how off-shell virtual particles underlie inflationary quantum fluctuations through the energy-time uncertainty relations.

Twistor-theoretic and double copy extensions to nonperturbative curved spacetime [55-57] could be useful for many applications, but on this view the linearized metric is required for the gravitational field based in classical double copy cohomology to be considered quantized gravitation. Nonlinearized metrics are usually considered more fundamental than linearized metrics in quantized gravity; for instance, Penrose suggests that gravitons cannot be described with a linearized metric since "with such a perturbative viewpoint it is only after an infinite number of 'gravitons' have been added that the space can become curved" [58]. However, the study of linearized metrics could be considered as nascent until discovery of the twistor Weyl double copy suggested that linearized metrics can be exact, vacuum, and sheaf-cohomological. Rather than a physical graviton as gravitational boson the graviton arising in the exact linearized vacuum metrics seems to be more of a methodological graviton (still of spin-2) helpful for studying implications of quantized gravity from twistor Weyl double copy.

Discussion—The argument arriving at the notion of Newman-Janis reality condition suggests that Penrose's twistor program can connect the double copy literature to Bell inequalities to help organize quantized gravity theories. A key aspect of the content-prediction interpretation of Bell inequalities is that it allows gravitational field quantization from the Penrose transform to not require considerations of quantum prediction since only quantum content is contained in the twistor sheaf cohomology. Only quantum content is contained in twistor sheaf cohomology since Bell inequalities distinguish geometric/physical type quantum content from physical type quantum prediction and twistor sheaf cohomology is geometric. Then linearized gravitation can be considered quantized gravitation without requiring consideration of quantum prediction. The question of the complex origin of twistor theory is resolved by the requirement of a geometric type of quantum content that extends physical-type quantum content (EPR) to sheaf-cohomological geometry mapping to gravitation.

On this view Bell inequalities solve the key aspects of quantum interpretation as required from the quantized gravity perspective, and the Copenhagen interpretation is a supplement to Bell inequalities that attempts to articulate reasoning limits arising when considering the quantum content side of Bell inequalities from the perspective of the quantum prediction side. The Copenhagen interpretation can be helpful to articulate conceptual difficulties arising from the empirical distinction between local content and local prediction; for instance, when focused on quantum prediction there could be some aspects (such as the Born rule, definition of measurement, or complementary relations) that seem incomprehensible solely because these aspects are perhaps fully clarified only from the geometric/physical perspective of quantum content, which is a perspective Bell and Aspect have shown is empirically inaccessible when focused on quantum prediction. The content-prediction interpretation of Bell inequalities suggests that hidden variables are not required to "restore completeness, determinism and causality to the [quantum] theory" [13, Section 1] since these classical features can be retained alongside quantum features such as entanglement or indeterminism by allowing that twistor cohomology can fully contain quantum content when mapping to linearized gravitational fields from the Kerr-Schild double copy. These twistor linearized gravitational fields are quantized in the sense that quantum content is contained in sheaf cohomology physically characterizing obstructions to lifting a local theory to a global theory, and that the linearized metric through Penrose transform is independent of consideration of quantum prediction.

The worldsheet effective action from consideration of the Newman-Janis transformation [33] suggests further connections between string and twistor theories given the applicability of string worldsheets to the interface of quantum information and gravity and to quantized gravity. The sheaf-cohomological foundations of twistor-theoretic fields seem as close as is possible for mathematical physics to intersect with the modern algebraic-geometric foundations in Grothendieck's Tôhoku theorem cohomologically relating the category of sheaves to the category of groups [59]. It is unanswered whether there is a unifying cohomology theory for the unambiguous radiative cohomology [3] and unambiguous nonradiative cohomology [4]; a result showing the impossibility of a unified cohomology could help distinguish radiative and nonradiative gravitational aspects.

Since quantum content is contained in cohomology only gravitational prediction is required for both gravity and quantized gravity theories, so the meaning of a limit between gravity and quantized gravity is not as clear when quantized gravity is cohomologically-based linearized gravity from Penrose transform. It would be especially interesting if this limit between gravity and linearized (quantized) gravity from Penrose transform could be resolved by consideration of cohomology of sheaves higher than first cohomology [5, 20]. A more physical approach to cohomological aspects of a limit between gravitation and quantized gravitation is from considering curved Kerr-Schild metrics such as on a de Sitter background [56, 57]. These curved Kerr-Schild metrics reduce to the linearized Kerr-Schild metrics as the cosmological constant approaches 0; therefore the cosmological constant approaching 0 can be considered a geometrizing of the Kerr-Schild graviton since the Penrose transform (sheaf cohomology) for linearized fields is applicable in limit. The cosmological constant, such as in the Friedmann equations, has positive energy density since some energy is required to convert the geometric linearized Kerr-Schild background in the Penrose transform to a physical curved Kerr-Schild de Sitter background. On this view the quantum field vacuum energy should be larger than the cosmological constant since the cosmological constant arises from removing sheaf-cohomological aspects of the linearized metric while the quantum content is within the sheaf cohomology as geometric local-global obstruction; therefore the quantum content is prior to the removal of sheaf-cohomology by cosmological constant and the quantum field vacuum energy is expected to be larger (significantly larger if the cohomology-'physicalizing' process from Minkowski to de Sitter background by including a cosmological constant is comparatively low energy).

Curved Kerr-Schild metrics are type A when the background is also double copied from Minkowski to curved space and type B when both sides have the same curved background [56, 57]. The gauge side of the classical double copy necessitates unambiguous cohomology so the gauge field can be considered as underlying the gravity field since in all possible (twistor-theoretic) worlds the unambiguous cohomology for gravitation is based in a double copy. Since the classical gauge field has Minkowski background it follows that perhaps type A curved Kerr-Schild metrics are more suitable when the double copy is classical and based in the ambiguities of twistor cohomology products. Then the starting notion of the Kerr-Schild double copy seems to be of the single copy gauge field on Minkowski background since the gauge squaring necessitates unambiguous cohomology for the gravity field and so underlies the gravity field. The Liénard-Wiechert field for a single moving charged particle is known to be a necessary form for the single copy of linearized Kerr-Schild metrics [60]. The cohomology mapping to electromagnetic field through Penrose transform contains quantum content geometrically and

is able to map to physical fields, but there needs to be a physical account of how the electromagnetic field connects to quantum content for the quantum content interpretation of twistor cohomology to be plausible. The account begins with interpreting Dirac's theory of electrodynamics as connecting the electromagnetic field to quantum theory in both quantum content and quantum prediction. Chandrasekhar's proof of the separation of the Dirac equation by Kerr geometry [61], building on Teukolsky's theory of Kerr separability [62], can then (by its relation to the electromagnetic field at the base of the Kerr-Schild double copy) be considered a key characteristic of the Kerr metric as quantum-gravitational. Kerr separability of equations can be interpreted as physical understanding (quantum-gravitational) since the quantum equations are 'factored' into natural components by Kerr geometry. The many well-known and remarkable aspects of the Kerr metric—such as those regarding separability of electromagnetic, neutrino, and gravitational field equations [62] or equivalence with three-point minimal coupling [32]—can be attributed to an emphasis on the Kerr metric as the main part of the Newman-Janis reality condition from content-prediction (twistor-theoretic) interpretation of Bell inequalities. "Problems associated with an electron in the vicinity of Kerr black holes" [61] can then perhaps be interpreted as the basic problems of quantized gravity suggesting that quantized gravity may be a theory at the foundations of chemistry rather than the foundations of physics.

Conclusion—Connections between twistor cohomology and the double copy suggest that the twistor Weyl double copy implies a linearized gravity interpretation of quantized gravity. The local interpretation of Bell inequalities distinguishes local quantum content from local quantum prediction suggesting that quantized gravity theories physically characterize the geometric obstruction to lifting a local theory to a global theory. Twistor theory's Penrose transform maps from twistor sheaf cohomology to physical fields and can be considered as necessitated by ambiguities in the cohomology product on the electromagnetic side of the classical double copy. The Kerr-Schild case of the Weyl double copy implies the Newman-Janis deformation as quantized gravity reality condition characterizing the differences between Schwarzschild and Kerr metrics. The Newman-Janis reality condition can perhaps help guide quantized gravity applications from a perspective emphasizing an ontology of elementary Kerr particles [32] and dynamics of worldsheet effective action [33].

The twistor monopole expansion seems a central notion to further study of basic twistor-theoretic aspects of the Kerr-Schild double copy since the expansion articulates a pairwise (twistor-theoretic) similarity between gauge and vacuum gravity field monopole moments [64, 65], and the twistor monopole expansion plays a key role in calculating (from three-point minimally coupled amplitudes) the Killing-Yano and Kerr curvature tensors central to conservation of energy and conservation of angular momentum [41]. Developments of split signature methods [32, 41, 42, 63] can perhaps address further connections between the amplitude and classical double copies to refine understanding and implications of Kerr-Schild metrics and the Newman-Janis deformation in relation to twistor cohomology [5, 18].

This paper interprets the discovery of twistor-cohomological aspects of the classical double copy. Double copy aspects of twistor theory in quantized gravity can be continually questioned by studying whether twistors can be proven not unique among mathematical-physical objects in allowing for maps to Kerr-Schild metrics from unambiguous sheaf cohomology necessitated by gauge squaring. Such a proof would disprove the necessity of a twistor-cohomological foundation for the classical double copy rather than disproving the relevance of the classical

double copy for quantized gravity. If a different mathematical object other than twistors allows for unambiguous sheaf-cohomological mapping to physical fields necessitated by a double copy based in the electromagnetic field then the requirements are still satisfied: that quantum content is expressed geometrically as characterizing obstruction from lifting a quantum theory to a linearized vacuum gravitation theory, and that consideration of quantum prediction is independent of quantized gravity as linearized gravity by the content-prediction interpretation of Bell inequalities distinguishing quantum geometric/physical content from quantum physical prediction.

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